

STUDYING THE PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' DIGITAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis of the rapid development of digital technologies and their application in everyday life, professional activities, and the educational process, the concepts of "competence" and "competency", "digital competence" and the scientific work of researchers on preparing learners to use information technologies.*

Keywords: *competence, competency, digital competence, information literacy, computer literacy, internet literacy.*

Today's globalization and digital transformation process are making the effective use of digital technologies in the education system increasingly relevant. In particular, the issue of training students in higher education institutions as specialists with digital competence, independent thinking and algorithmic thinking, meeting the requirements of the modern labor market, is one of the priority areas of state education policy.

The digital transformation processes currently taking place in all spheres of society are causing fundamental changes in various aspects of human activity, including the education system. As a result of the rapid development of digital technologies and their widespread introduction into everyday life, professional activities and the educational process, digital competence is considered one of the most important professional and social qualities of a person.

The development of students' digital competence, on the one hand, requires the formation of their skills in searching, analyzing and processing information, and on the other hand, requires the development of creative and critical thinking, independent decision-making abilities in problem situations. Therefore, the issue of forming this competence is not only a technical or methodological approach, but also a comprehensive socio-pedagogical problem.

The need for students to quickly search, find and process new information related to their specialty in their professional activities requires the development of their professional competencies such as information and communication, design, construction, management and research. There is also a need to improve digital competence through innovative educational technologies based on the formation of skills for self-activation, management and assessment, independent learning throughout life, mastering foreign languages, critical analysis of activities, teamwork, decision-making and constant search for new ideas and technologies.

Initially, it is appropriate to clarify the difference between the concepts of "competence" and "competency". The word "competence" is derived from the Latin "compete", which means to achieve, to match, to approach, to strive for. The word "competency" comes from the Latin "competens", which means to be suitable, to belong to. From a linguistic point of view, the main difference between these concepts is considered to be the parts of speech of the words from which they are formed. Accordingly, the concept of "competence" reflects a verbal action or skill.

According to foreign researchers, the concept of digital competence consists of a set of skills and competencies focused on several areas, such as media and communication, technology

and computer work, literacy and information sciences. Digital competence includes such components as the ability to fully use digital technologies, technical skills for using digital technologies, working in various types of activities, the ability to critically evaluate digital technologies, motivation to be part of digital culture in education and everyday life [1].

According to the model of competence in the public administration system of the Digital Transformation Group, digital competence is the ability of a user to confidently, effectively and safely select and apply information and communication technologies in various areas of life. It consists of information search based on the constant acquisition of knowledge, skills, motivation, responsibility, using digital devices, using the functional capabilities of social networks, online shopping, critical perception of information, financial transactions, production of multimedia content, synchronization of devices, etc. [2].

Digital competence have a structural structure. Digital competencies include components such as knowledge, skills and attitudes (motivation and responsibility). Each component is implemented in different areas of activity in the digital environment.

G.U.Soldatova's psychological model of digital competence includes considering digital competencies not only as a set of knowledge and skills, but also as effective activity based on a sense of responsibility and the establishment of a personal attitude to it [3]. This component determines the effectiveness and safety of using digital technologies in activities. Among the components of digital competence, it highlights knowledge, skills, motivation and responsibilities.

Summarizing the differences from the perspective of digital competence and digital competence, digital competence is based on the continuous acquisition of knowledge and skills, and is the ability of a person to confidently, effectively and safely select and use digital technologies in various areas of life. [4].

Since competencies are formed throughout life, tools are needed to determine the level of formation of competencies in the process of continuous education. The same applies to digital competence.

We distinguish between the concepts of digital literacy and digital competence. Some researchers consider these terms to be close in meaning and use them interchangeably. This term appeared before the term "digital competence". Jones-Cavalier and Flannigan believe that digital literacy refers to the ability of a person to effectively perform tasks in a digital environment. Digital means that information is presented in digital forms and used on a computer, and literacy includes the ability to read and interpret content, reproduce data and images through digital manipulation, and evaluate and extract new knowledge from the digital environment[1].

Scientific research and analysis of sources on the topic of the study show that with the development of new modern technologies, new terms such as "information literacy", "computer literacy", "Internet literacy", "media literacy", "multimedia literacy" have emerged, the common feature of which is that they are related to the effective use of digital resources in learning, and all of them are components of digital literacy[5].

Based on the studied materials, we formulate a specific definition of digital competence. Digital competence is not just the ability to use technical means, but also a person's readiness to search for, analyze, process information, create new knowledge and products, collaborate online, and ensure information security using digital technologies. In this regard, I have cited the author's definition that the development of digital competence in students is one of the strategic priorities of higher education.

In our country, in order to effectively organize a system for training specialists in the field

of information technologies as active, creative thinkers, inquisitive, independently searching for the necessary information, and able to apply it in their practical activities, it is necessary to pay special attention to their information and communication competencies[6].

To date, the implementation of digital technologies in higher education institutions is at a very low level, and a new stage of development in Uzbekistan is the state of large-scale work on radically improving the teaching of information technologies based on the reforms being implemented in the education system, and through this, creating a system for training highly skilled and competitive personnel in the IT field. This can be largely explained by the unpreparedness of teachers of higher education institutions to use these technologies in the educational process[7].

The introduction of e-learning based on digital technologies will raise the quality of the educational process in educational institutions to a new level. Such an approach will allow students to effectively use modern digital tools and electronic educational materials, and will play a decisive role in the formation and strengthening of the necessary digital competencies for them.

Based on the research on the research problem, we have reviewed the research work of foreign researchers on preparing students to use information technologies.

I.Kh. Rozimurodov in his scientific research developed the main principles of professional competence formation in the e-learning environment [1].

P. Anderson, Namahnlar “conducted research in their research that e-learning creates opportunities for information exchange and knowledge sharing. They showed that the delivery of e-learning depends on applications and processes such as computers, web technologies, social networks, new educational technologies, Internet technologies” [8].

In the scientific research work of U.Kh.Mingboev on the topic “Improving the methodology for the formation of information and communicative competencies in students”, special emphasis is placed on the issues of scientific modeling of the process of forming information and communicative competencies of students, determining the pedagogical conditions that serve this process, and assessing the pedagogical potential of the discipline “Informatics and Information Technologies” that allow improving the methodology for the development of communicative competencies [9].

F.M.Zakirova covered the application of the methodology for creating electronic educational resources in teaching informatics and information technologies in the educational process, the use of methods and tools in teaching the subject, and the theoretical and practical foundations of methodological preparation of students in teaching informatics and information technologies in her research work [10].

The research reflects the integration factors of the formation of communicative competence of future engineering teachers based on the improvement of reflexive forms of professional communicative activity (individual-methodical, intuitive) with verbal and non-verbal means of pedagogical image (integration, constant analysis).

The above-mentioned analyses of our scientists show that today the preparation of a future engineer-pedagogue for professional pedagogical activity is in the first place. His preparation for professional pedagogical activity is determined by the ability to actively master modern pedagogical technologies and methods, the breadth of the scope of independent activity, the ability to design and correctly select pedagogical processes, the level of wide use of modern information and communication technologies in his future professional activity.

In conclusion, in the conditions of globalization and digital transformation, the

development of digital competence in students is one of the strategic tasks of the higher education system. Digital competence is manifested not only as a set of technical knowledge and skills, but also as a complex quality that includes the ability to search, analyze, process information, think critically and creatively, and carry out safe and responsible digital activities. The scientific sources analyzed in the study and the views of foreign and domestic scientists show that the development of digital competence requires a continuous educational process, the widespread introduction of innovative pedagogical approaches and e-learning technologies.

At the same time, the insufficient level of implementation of digital technologies in higher education institutions and the readiness of teachers to use digital educational tools remain a pressing problem. The digital competence of students can be effectively developed through the development of an electronic learning environment, the use of interactive and adaptive teaching technologies, as well as the systematic formation of information and communication competencies. As a result, the opportunity to train digitally competent, competitive, independent-thinking specialists who meet the requirements of the modern labor market will expand.

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